

Original Research

Digital Finance as a Catalyst for Sustainable Development in Nigeria

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Received 21 August 2025 Revised 21 December 2025 Accepted 7 January 2026
Published 1 April 2026

Abstract

This study used quarterly data from 2009 to 2023 to examine the nexus between digital finance and sustainable development in Nigeria. Ex post facto research design was used in this research. One dimension of sustainable development was considered in this study. This dimension was proxied by CO₂ tons per capita (measure of environmental sustainability). The number of commercial bank branches (NOB), Webpay (VWPAY), Automated Teller Machine (VATM), Point of Sale (VPOS), Mobile Payment (VMP), and individual access to the internet (IDT) were used as proxies for digital finance. The World Development Indicators and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin served as the sources of data. Estimation techniques include descriptive and correlation analyses, Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) and Error Correction Model (ECM). Hence, the findings indicate both short- and long-term period of interactions exist between digital finance and sustainable development in Nigeria. As a results, the ECM confirmed that short run disequilibrium was corrected in the long run at 35%. The study concluded that digital financial instruments played significant roles in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. It was therefore recommended among others, that the apex bank should provide sufficient digital finance directives to all financial institutions to adapt, embrace, and shift to digital technology in order to achieve sustainable development in Nigeria.

Keywords: ARDL, ATM, Mobile Banking, Online Banking, POS.

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Introduction

One of the recent global demands of technology is the digital finance. This is because financial system and economy are becoming more digital due to the rise in the use of digital payments (Mohan & Kumari, 2023). The unbanked rural people are anticipated to benefit from improved coverage and more affordable services through digital media such as ATMs, internet, E-Wallets, POS, and M-Banking. Thus, Nigeria's economy has an opportunity and privilege as digital finance and sustainable development interact within the country.

As postulated by the United Nations (2015), sustainable development has emerged as a top priority of the government policies in the recent time. This is because rapid urbanization, industrialization, and population growth have greatly raised the demand for natural resources (Lei *et al.*, 2023). Thus, it is generally accepted that integrating digital finance into economic framework is a wise approach to generate capital for sustainable development projects, which will allow the country to resist economic shocks and environmental issues (Okeke & Ibe, 2024).

Access to financial services facilitates and promotes industrial activity, which could possibly increase CO₂ emissions and cause global warming. Although Nigeria's economy is one of the fastest-growing in Africa, a sizable portion of the populace lacks access to formal financial services, official employment, and the capacity to engage in both online and offline paid labour activities, making financial exclusion a major constraint (Le *et al.*, 2020).

According to the recent scholarly research, digital finance is very essential in achieving Nigeria's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Adebisi *et al.*, 2023; Okoye & Eze, 2022). These studies, which address underprivileged populace, demonstrate how digital finance does not only enhance financial inclusion but also promote economic empowerment, reduce poverty, and foster conducive environment to sustained growth.

However, Nigeria faces numerous constraints in utilizing digital finance for sustainable development. These challenges include regulations, cybersecurity risks, low digital literacy, and dearth of infrastructure (Ajah & Chigozie-Okwum, 2019). Furthermore, the magnitude of banking activities today has significantly increased carbon emissions due to a number of causes, including air conditioning, lighting, paper waste, electrical and electronic equipment, and Information Technology (IT), despite the banking industry's historical reputation as a pollution-free industry. In view of this, several studies have been conducted to establish the significance of digital finance in developing economies around the world, yet inconclusive results were reported. The study by Adebisi *et al.*, (2023) found a negative and insignificant influence of webpay and point of sale (POS) on Nigeria's sustainable growth while Appah, Tebepah and Newstyle (2023) has proven that POS contributed positively to the growth of the Nigerian economy. Gharbi and Kammoun (2022) concluded that digital banking effectively enhanced the financial inclusion, thereby facilitating the growth of Tunisian economy. However, in South Asian, it was discovered by Sadiq and Ali (2024) that digital finance negatively affected environmental sustainability by increasing CO₂

emission. It is obvious that the discrepancies in the results was due to the inconsistency in the methodologies (such as GMM, VECM) utilized by the previous studies. Furthermore, some of these studies have failed to consider individual access to internet as an essential variable to facilitate efficient digital finance in developing country. This leaves huge gap in the literature to be filled by this study. Hence, how can digital finance be successfully used to advance sustainable development in Nigeria while taking into account the opportunities and challenges posed by the digital financial system? This study therefore employed ARDL technique to examine the impact of digital finance on sustainable development in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Digital Finance: Concepts and Tools

Digital finance has been conceptualized by Mohan and Kumari (2023) as the use of advanced digital technology to render traditional financial services including credit, transfers, and payments. Digital finance as opined by Agufa (2016), involve the arrangement money-related benefits, which requires the use of portable or web technologies as well as a team of experts. It is a computerized financial service which entails the use of less sophisticated technologies (such as the internet and flexible correspondence) to carry out budgetary transactions. Therefore, digital finance is a broad category of technologies that can be used to provide financial services to a large range of suppliers and recipients. Digital remote instruments such as e-money, mobile money, card payment, and electronic fund transfer are used to accomplish these activities (AbdulRaheem *et al.*, 2023), including the initiatives to promote inclusive finance through digital financial services.

Online lending services provide easy and speedy financing. This has created a more accessible lending environment, which make it possible for entrepreneurs and small businesses to have the capital they needed to grow. The integration of digital technology into financial sector has emerged as a crucial element for driving environmental change and creating opportunities for sustainable growth in the rapidly evolving realm of global finance (Idris *et al.*, 2022). This is particularly crucial in developing countries like Nigeria, where digital money offers a practical way to overcome long-standing challenges to financial inclusion, boost economic growth, and specifically address urgent environmental issues.

Sustainable Development (SD): Concepts and Goals

Since Sustainable Development (SD) requires dimensions and concepts, it is difficult to define (Mensah & Enu-Kwesi, 2018). It can be interpreted as "sustained change," "successful development," or "sustained growth" by others. As stated by Mohieldin (2017), SD is a method of development that uses resources in a way that let them exist for other people. Furthermore, it entails the process of addressing the recent demands without compromising the ability to meet the needs of future generations. As stated by Macaver (2018), the concept of sustainable development was addressed and incorporated into development economics during the Rio de Janeiro Earth Summit. This

was in reaction to the discovery that poverty does not only impedes development but also directly emanates from environmental damage.

Given the developing countries' social, economic, and environmental problems, sustainable development is an important concept in Nigeria and the world at large (Kim *et al.*, 2018). Hence, in Nigeria, poverty is one of most significant constraints. Reducing poverty must be the primary goal of sustainable development, with an emphasis on increasing access to education, employment and healthcare. This can be achieved by promoting economic growth and the emergence of green industries like agriculture and renewable energy.

Prior to the advancement of SDGs, the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) were a historical worldwide mobilization to achieve a set of social priorities (Breuer, Janetschek, & Malerba, 2019). Despite the efficacy of MDGs, none of the eight goals were met after implementation for 15 years (i.e. 2000-2015). Thus, to continue with the development agenda, there is a call for SDGs' implementation (Taylor, 2016), which are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: SDGs by the United Nations (2015)

One major issue threatening the health of our planet is environmental degradation. As a result, a number of studies take into account the factors influencing environmental sustainability in the some of the existing literature. Digital finance is one of the main variables being considered at the moment among the factors. However, the 3Ps, including the People, Planet, and Profits are essential to achieving sustainable environment and growth, which is one of the three facets of SD that led to the creation of the 17 SDGs. Customer behaviour is therefore the primary driver and determinant of the shift to green banking (Yu *et al.*, 2022).

Theoretical Review

The essential roles of digital finance or technology in improving economy and sustaining environment had been postulated by Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) which was advocated by Fred Davis (1986) and Capability Approach (supporting theory). As postulated by the TAM, people are more inclined to accept modern technology because of their perception that it will improve the economy, protect the environment, and create jobs and due to the fact that it is simple to use or adopt. Since the digital finance include online payments, mobile banking, fintech services, digital wallet etc, individual are likely to adopt it as pointed out by the TAM theory if they are certain that it will increase access to credit, improves convenience and facilitates financial management. On the other hand, the capacity approach asserted that people possess a variety of talents and abilities that enable them to transform resources into worthwhile accomplishments, and that personal freedom to pursue desired results serves as a gauge of progress. Since the capability approach is centered on human capability rather than the resources they possess, digital finance allows people to invest, save, insure and transact, especially the underserved communities. This enables individuals to participate in economy, manage risk and gain more control over their finances. Government therefore embrace technology because they believe it helps achieve the desired objectives of sustainable development (Ozili, 2018).

Empirical Review

Scholars and researchers have differing opinions about the relationship between sustainable development and digital finances. One of them demonstrated how the introduction of new technology in digital finance alters conventional methods and improves environmental sustainability (Ozili, 2018; Salman & Ismael, 2022). According to another studies, digital finance might drive growth, which would increase carbon dioxide emissions (Ozturk & Ullah, 2022). Consequently, predicting how digital banking will affect CO₂ emissions is very difficult.

Echu *et al.*, (2024) analyzed how digital finance promotes sustainable growth in Nigeria. A positivist method was utilized with a sample size of 384 people to accomplish the objectives of the study. Regression analysis was used to analyze the data and investigate the connections between digital finance and sustainable growth. The study therefore established that digital finance significant interacted with SD measures in Nigeria. However, in Tunisia, Gharbi and Kammoun, (2022) examined how digital finance influence financial inclusion using e-wallets, online banking, mobile banking, and ATMs as sampled variables. The study is unique because it uses different measures of inclusive development such as access, quality, and efficiency of financial services to investigate the connection between digital banking and financial inclusion. The study discovered a significant correlation between digital technology and financial inclusion.

Qin *et al.*, (2021), and Adebisi *et al.*, (2023) found that financial development has improved by digitization in financial institutions, which in turn enhance sustainable growth. According to the study of Ali *et al.*, (2021), DFI contributes to an increase in per capita GDP, and reduces energy consumption. Zhao, Zheng and Li (2022) found that the adoption of digital finance and digitization reduce CO₂ emissions by reducing

energy consumption and increasing per capita income. Digital finance affects CO₂ emissions more broadly when it is used for payments and investments. Udeagha and Ngepah (2023) established that financial technology can assist nations in transitioning to a green economy by expanding the amount of capital for environmentally friendly initiatives and reducing the transaction costs related to financing green development projects.

Research Methods

Data Source and Analytical Technique

This research used quarterly and secondary data from 2009 to 2023. The data source was employed in line with the studies of Adebisi *et al.*, (2023) and Sadiq and Ali (2024). The study adopted environmental sustainability, which one of the three dimensions of sustainable development as the dependent variable. This is because digital finance directly influences sustainable environment in developing countries like Nigeria. The environment sustainability was proxied by CO₂ tons per capita and the regressors include the number of commercial bank branches, ATM, POS, mobile payment, and individual internet access. The data were culled from the World Development Indicator and the CBN statistical bulletin. Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique was used with the aids of EViews package.

Theoretical Framework and Models

This study rests on the assumptions of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). This is because the hypothesis emphasizes on the acceptance or rejection of technology due to the people's attitudes, beliefs, actual use and intentions. According to the theory, the user acceptance of technology is influenced by two major beliefs, including perceive ease of use and perceived usefulness. People's belief that a particular system can provide and boost job performance can lead to the acceptance of the system. Hence, in relations to the digital finance, using digital finance platform such as digital payments, mobile banking and other services, which was facilitated by digital instruments (such as POS) has helped to boost job opportunities and reduced paper work, thereby influencing sustainable development. TAM provides a well-structured mechanism that connect digital financial adoption with sustainable development, where the ease of use and perceive usefulness of technology facilitate sustained growth, social equity and environmental sustainability of different countries.

Functionally, TAM can be summarized as follows:

$$AU = f(PU, PEOU, ATU, BI) \quad (1)$$

Where AU implies the possible behavioural outcome, BI is the intentions of the people, ATU represents the attitude function while PU and PEOU are the belief functions of the people, which are the key determinants of the TAM. Hence, this model was substituted for digital financial instruments and SD indicator to establish the linkage between digital finance and sustainable development in Nigeria. The model is remodified as follows:

$$ES = f(VATM, VPOS, VMB, VWPAY, NOB, IDT) \quad (2)$$

Due to the nature of dependent variable, the regressors were transformed into logarithm forms. Hence, the model is stated as follows:

$$ES = f(LVATM, LVPOS, LVMB, LVWPAY, LNOB, LIDT) \quad (3)$$

$$ES = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LVATM + \beta_2 LVPOS + \beta_3 LVMB + \beta_3 LVWPAY + \beta_3 LNOB + \beta_3 LIDT + \mu \quad (4)$$

The model is further written in ARDL form:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta ES = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{t=1}^{p1} \alpha_1 \Delta ES + \sum_{t=1}^{p2} \alpha_2 \Delta LVATM_{t-1} + \sum_{t=1}^{p3} \alpha_3 \Delta LVPOS_{t-1} + \\ & \sum_{t=1}^{p4} \alpha_4 \Delta LVMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t=1}^{p5} \alpha_5 \Delta LVWPAY_{t-1} + \sum_{t=1}^{p6} \alpha_6 \Delta LNOB_{t-1} + \sum_{t=1}^{p7} \alpha_7 \Delta LIDT_{t-1} + \\ & \beta_1 ES_{t-1} + \beta_2 LVATM_{t-1} + \beta_3 LVPOS_{t-1} + \beta_4 LVMB_{t-1} + \beta_5 LVWPAY_{t-1} + \\ & \beta_6 LVNOB_{t-1} + \beta_7 LIDT_{t-1} + \lambda ECM_{it-1} + \mu \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where, ES is the Co₂ ton percapita (proxy of sustainable development); the log Automated Teller Machine was referred to as LVATM; LVPOS connoted the log of Point of Sales, the log of Mobile Payment was denoted as LVMP; the log of Webpay (LVWPAY), the individual access to internet was proxied as LIDT while LNOB is the number of commercial bank branches. Similarly, β_0 implies constant term; $\beta_1 - \beta_7$ is the long-run coefficient; $\alpha_1 - \alpha_7$ means coefficient of short-term periods; μ is the error term and t_{-1} represents the time lag.

Results

Descriptive Statistics of Variables

The characteristics of the volumes of ATM, POS, webpay, and mobile payment, access to internet and commercial bank branches under study were displayed in Table 1. The mean and median of the variable exhibit a high degree of stability, which are in tandem with the findings. As expected, the volume of ATM reflects the highest value, followed by the volume of POS. Furthermore, the ATM exhibits a high value for the standard deviation, followed by the individual access to internet, which explain extent of variability. From Jarque-Bera statistics, it was discovered that Co₂ per capita, the volume of POS, the volume of mobile payment, and access to internet are normally distributed while the VATM, the VWebpay and commercial bank branches are not normally distributed overtime.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

	ES	LVATM	LVPOS	LVMP	LVWPAY	LNOB	LIDT
Mean	0.59	20.06	17.89	17.65	17.71	8.605	3.29
Median	0.59	20.19	17.96	17.65	16.45	8.606	3.34
Max	0.67	21.25	22.11	21.40	23.39	8.67	4.02
Min	0.49	17.76	13.70	13.86	14.24	8.48	2.14
Std. Dev.	0.04	0.92	2.81	2.33	3.35	0.04	0.58
Skew	-0.29	-0.97	-0.04	-0.072	0.71	-1.13	-0.33
Kurtosis	3.85	3.41	1.72	1.87	1.91	4.36	1.82
Jar-Bera	2.64	9.77	4.08	3.19	8.04	17.30	4.57
Prob	0.27	0.01	0.13	0.20	0.02	0.00	0.10
Sum	35.48	1203.65	1073.97	1059.49	1062.76	516.18	197.69
Sum Sq.	0.075	50.27	465.94	322.91	662.56	0.11	20.02
Obs.	60	60	60	60	60	60	60

Correlation Analysis

The results of correlation analysis were presented in Table 2. This statistic evaluates the extent of collinearity among the regressors being examined. There is high correlation between the digital financial tools except individual access to internet which exhibit a negative association with the commercial bank branches. Similarly, a moderate and negative correlation was found between the volume of POS and the number of commercial bank branches. A negative correlation was also seen between the volume of mobile payment and the number of commercial bank branches. The reason for the high correlations between the digital financial instruments is not far-fetched because these instruments serve the same purpose and are associated with each other while facilitating financial transactions of the customers.

Table 2: Correlation Statistics

Var	ES	LVATM	LVPOS	LVMP	LVWPAY	LNOB	LIDT
ES	1.00						
LVATM	0.10	1.00					
LVPOS	-0.01	0.91	1.00				
LVMP	0.03	0.90	0.98	1.00			
LVWPAY	-0.28	0.80	0.92	0.91	1.00		
LNOB	0.21	-0.62	-0.59	-0.59	-0.66	1.00	
LIDT	0.05	0.92	0.98	0.96	0.88	-0.54	1.00

ADF Unit Root Test

To ensure that the analytical process was accurately used, all the data were subjected to a unit root test using the ADF method. Table 3 showed that the number of commercial bank branches is stationary at level I(0) at 5% threshold. However, the volume of ATMs, POS systems, mobile payments, webpay, individual internet connection and environmental sustainability (measured by CO₂ emissions) are all

significant at first difference I (1). Hence, the model is appropriate for ARDL estimation technique and freed from erroneous findings.

Table 3: Stationarity Test

Null Hypothesis: the variable has a unit root								
Unit Root @ Level								
		ES	LVATM	LVPOS	LVMP	LVWPAY	LNOB	LIDT
With Constant	t-Stats	-1.095	-1.306	-0.643	-1.581	-1.063	0.384	-1.857
	Prob.	0.710	0.619	0.851	0.485	0.723	0.980	0.349
		n0	n0	n0	n0	n0	n0	n0
Without Constant & Trend	t-Stats	-0.562	1.603	1.276	1.689	1.186	-1.968	1.607
	Prob.	0.468	0.971	0.947	0.976	0.938	0.047	0.972
		n0	n0	n0	n0	n0	**	n0
Unit Root @ First Difference								
		d(ES)	d(LVATM)	d(LVPOS)	d(LVMP)	d(LVWPAY)	d(LNOB)	d(LIDT)
With Constant	t-Stats	-3.110	-2.622	-3.515	-3.135	-3.188	-3.799	-2.651
	Prob.	0.032	0.095	0.011	0.029	0.025	0.005	0.088
		**	*	**	**	**	***	*
Without Constant & Trend	t-Stats	-3.187	-2.110	-1.649	-2.368	-1.688	-3.230	-1.654
	Prob.	0.002	0.034	0.093	0.018	0.086	0.001	0.092

(*) Significant at the 10%; (**) at the 5%; (***) at the 1%; and (no) Not Significant

Lag Selection Criteria

Table 4 showed the results of the lag selection, which was conducted to determine the proper lag for the variables (both dependent and explanatory variables). According to the AIC criterion, Lag 5 was assumed to be more suitable for the analysis.

Table 4: Lag Selection Criteria

Lag	Log L	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	56.71544	NA	3.87e-10	-1.807834	-1.552355	-1.709038
1	621.8533	965.8721	2.77e-18	-20.57649	-18.53266	-19.78612
2	718.5783	140.6908	5.32e-19	-22.31194	-18.47976	-20.83000
3	750.7174	38.56689	1.24e-18	-21.69881	-16.07828	-19.52531
4	820.1415	65.63732	9.68e-19	-22.44151	-15.03262	-19.57643
5	1443.014	430.3480*	2.22e-27*	-43.30959*	-34.11235*	-39.75294*

ARDL Short Run and Long Run Results

Table 5 displayed the coefficient of the explanatory variables and the CO₂ per capita (dependent variable). To explain the current situation of digital finance and sustainable development in Nigeria, only the lag value of CO₂ per capita and the current periods of the regressors were examined. The coefficients of LVATM, LVWPAY, LNOB, and LIDT interact negatively with the CO₂ per capita. This suggests that the CO₂ per capita will decrease by -0.0077, -0.0227, -0.1354, and -0.404 units for every unit increase in each of the variables stated. However, there is a favorable correlation between CO₂ per capita and both POS and mobile payment. This indicates that there is a possible 0.0293 and 0.022 unit increase in CO₂ per capita for every unit increase in POS and mobile payment respectively.

Table 5: ARDL Results

Var	Coeff	Std Error	Prob
ES (-1)	1.011	0.005	0.0000
LVATM	-0.0077	0.0004	0.0000
LVPOS	0.0293	0.0012	0.0000
LVMP	0.022	0.0004	0.0000
LVWPAY	-0.0227	0.0002	0.0000
LNOB	-0.1354	0.0066	0.0000
LIDT	-0.4040	0.0223	0.0000
C	-0.1201	0.0255	0.0004
R ²	0.99		
Adj R ²	0.99		
F-Stats	215617.6		0.000000
Bound: F-Stats	7878.71		
5% Lower	2.45		
Upper	3.61		
ECM	-0.35		

Based on the t-statistic results, every digital financial instrument has a strong and significant influence on Nigeria's sustainable development. The model's goodness of fit of 99% was explained by both adjusted R² and R², while the error term captured the remaining 1% variation in the model. A long-term connection between the predictors and the predicting variable was confirmed by the f-statistics of ARDL Bound test. The value shows 7878.71, which exceeded the upper bound value of 3.61 established a long run relationship among the variables. Thereafter, an ECM analysis was conducted and it was discovered that short disequilibrium was addressed at a rate of 35%.

Discussions

The features of the variables under review were displayed in Table 1. The mean and median of the series show a high degree of stability. As anticipated, the volume of ATM reflects the highest mean value, next to the volume of POS. This is a sign of increasing acceptance and usage of automated teller machine and point of sale in carrying financial

transaction in the Nigeria's economy over the years. The automated teller machine exhibits a high value for the standard deviation, followed by the individual access to internet, which gauges the degree of variability. Given the current state of the economy, it is not surprising that fluctuation in the operation of ATM is the main topic of discussion among citizens as the Nigerian government recently introduced the ATM charges for financial transaction outside the users' bank branches. Thus, a shift in economic policy has an impact on the degree of ATM's usage by the customers. From the results of the Jarque-Bera statistics, it was observed that sustainable development (proxy of CO₂ emission), the volume of POS, the volume of mobile payment, and access to internet are normally distributed while the volumes of ATM and webpay, as well as, commercial bank branches are not normally distributed for the period under review.

From the ARDL results, the coefficients of LVWPAY, LVATM, LIDT and LNOB negatively associated with the CO₂ per capita. However, there is a positive correlation between CO₂ per capita and both POS and mobile payment volumes. These results were in accordance with the work of Ozili, (2018); Salman and Ismael (2022); and Echu *et al.*, (2024). The t-statistic shows that, all the digital finance instruments have significant impact on sustainable development in Nigeria. This finding was supported by the TAM theory as it was shown that individual embrace technology due to it benefits and how it facilitates economic development. The results are also in line with a priori expectation of the study. Furthermore, it was established that long run relationship exists among the variables. This necessitated the conduct of error correction analysis. The ECM analysis confirmed that short term disequilibrium was corrected at 35%. The results corroborate the findings of Ali *et al.*, (2021) as it was reported that digital money had a bigger impact on per capital GDP.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the analysis which specified that digital finance has short run and long run impact on sustainable development, it was therefore concluded that digital financial instruments are the ingredients of sustainable development in Nigeria. Hence, the study recommends that:

The apex bank should provide sufficient digital finance directives to all financial institutions to adapt, embrace, and shift to digital technology to achieve sustainable development in Nigeria.

Since digital finance has been the key driver for funding projects that promote environmental sustainability, government should create incentives for investments in green projects through digital platforms.

In an attempt to encourage digital finance to improve financial inclusion and inclusive growth of the country, policy makers should implement strict regulations to fight against high rate of cybercrimes to ensure effective and efficient operations of online banking, mobile banking and ATM.

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<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Olayiwola, H. Olaniyi and Sanyaolu, S. O. (2026). Digital Finance as a Catalyst for Sustainable Development in Nigeria. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 13(4), 497-510. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2026.540166.1833</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_242065.html</p>	